

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND MODULES IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS

Ilhomjon Aldashev

Teacher of Fergana state university

Zarnigorbonu Toyirjonova

Student, Fergana State University of Foreign languages

Abstract: In the article, information technology's which are taught to students role in the teaching process as well as the most crucial standings of particular technological modules and the achievements in this regard are analyzed.

Key words: information technology, application modules, informatics management, technical tools, sites, EBA and FAITH stores.

In modern society, the field of informatics plays a crucial role in modern society by leveraging technology and data to drive innovation, efficiency, and problem-solving across various sectors. Here are some key roles of informatics in modern society. Informatics helps in collecting, storing, organizing, and analyzing vast amounts of data, leading to better decision-making and insights. In healthcare, informatics enables the management of patient data, electronic health records, telemedicine, and medical research, ultimately improving patient care and outcome. In addition, informatics is used for managing financial transactions, analyzing market trends, optimizing operations, and developing strategies for business growth. It is clear that in education, informatics supports e-learning, data analysis for student performance, administrative tasks automation, and personalized learning experiences. Informatics provide students with the large number of chances in terms of communication field. Informatics tools and technologies facilitate seamless communication through social media, messaging apps, email services, video conferencing, and collaboration platforms. Research and development systems are related to this field as well. Informatics accelerates research processes by facilitating data collection, analysis, visualization, and collaboration among researchers in various disciplines. There are the number of benefits of informatics in cybersecurity field. Informatics plays a crucial role in safeguarding digital assets, networks, and systems from cyber threats, ensuring data privacy and security. As well as informatics is essential for developing smart city infrastructures, optimizing resource

utilization, improving transportation systems, and enhancing overall urban living conditions.

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